

Supplementary material

for

Identifying the socio-demographic profile of household used cooking oil recyclers in 10 Municipalities in Greece

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Figure S1. Municipalities under study in the research article ‘Identifying the socio-demographic profile of household used cooking oil recyclers in 10 Municipalities in Greece’ (adapted from the ‘Municipalities’ boundaries’ shapefile by Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT), 2015).

Figure S2. Analytical workflow of the statistical methods applied

Chi-Square Test Assumptions and Hypothesis Formulation

To investigate the association between the IV_i and the DV_j , initially an X^2 test for association was employed. The three out four necessary assumptions for applying this statistical test were fulfilled in all cases: the tested variables are categorical, the observations are considered independent (see below justification) and a cross-sectional sampling was used. For all cases, except educational attainment and employment status, there were no more than 20% of the expected cells frequencies less than five. To address this issue, the number of categories for these two variables were reduced. The H_0 was “no association between variables” and the H_A was “an association exists between variables”.

Table S1. Interpretation of Cramer's V and ϕ_c (Akoglu, 2018)

Cramer's V and ϕ_c values	Interpretation
>0.25	Very strong
>0.15	Strong
>0.10	Moderate
>0.05	Weak
>0	No or very weak

Addressing Data Imbalance in Logistic Regression Model

After the encoding of the DV_2 , the dataset was split into two groups, a training set (70%, 2,100) and a testing set (30%, 900), by using stratified sampling, ensuring that the proportion of participants and non-participants is maintained in both the training and testing sets. This split ratio was chosen to ensure robust evaluation and capture a larger number of examples from the minority class in both the training and test datasets (Bichri et al., 2024; Rácz et al., 2021). Variables were standardised using the Standard Scaler technique to ensure that every variable has an equal impact on the model, minimizing the likelihood of bias towards those with greater values. This technique altered the variables to achieve a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one.

A range of methods for managing data imbalance and attaining optimal results was examined (figure S2). Both types of data - weighted and unweighted - were analysed, and the threshold for categorising predicted probabilities was adjusted as appropriate. The model performance was evaluated using the following set of metrics: accuracy, precision, recall (sensitivity), f1-score, and ROC AUC.

The following Logistic Regression (LR) models were created and evaluated: a) a baseline LR model without addressing the class imbalance, b) a LR model with post-stratification weights to adjust for sample representativeness, c) a LR model employing the SMOTE technique to oversample the minority class, d) a LR model using the LDA technique, and e) for comparative purposes, models using other techniques like Random Forest and XGBoost (other techniques were also used, but they are not presented here).

The baseline LR, despite its high accuracy rate, reveals a significant weakness in identifying potential participants, as indicated by its low recall, which points to a bias favouring the majority class in its predictions. The use of sample weights led to a decline in accuracy and a significant drop in recall, indicating that simply applying weights does not adequately resolve the imbalance in this situation. The application of SMOTE technique showed an improvement in recall, suggesting a greater capacity to recognise true participants, though this came with the trade-off of smaller overall accuracy, indicating a likelihood of more false positive predictions.

Modifying the classification threshold, failed to improve the model's performance.

According to the findings from the applied techniques, the most effective model was generated through the SMOTE method. After utilizing SMOTE with a 1:1 oversampling ratio, the test set remained unchanged for unbiased evaluation, the minority class expanded to 1,850 observations, leading to an overall sample count of 3,750. The post-SMOTE LR model achieved an accuracy of 0.778, which is slightly lower than the accuracy of the baseline LR model before SMOTE (0.881). However, and crucially, metrics more relevant to imbalanced datasets showed substantial improvement after SMOTE. For instance, recall increased from 0.000 to 0.383, precision from 0.000 to 0.234, and F1-score from 0.000 to 0.291. The original accuracy, prior to data splitting and the application of SMOTE, stood at 88.1%; however, the results were distorted by the imbalance, causing the minority class to seem significantly less frequent than it actually was.

The precision level of 0.234 suggests a considerable occurrence of false positives, indicating that the model finds it challenging to distinguish recyclers apart from non-recyclers. The model's f1-score of 0.291 indicates a significant difficulty in effectively distinguishing actual recyclers and that the model makes possibly incorrect predictions. With a moderate ROC AUC of 0.65, the model outperforms random selection, but it still demonstrates a lack of strong differentiation between the categories. A Nagelkerke R-squared of 0.335 suggests that, although it is within an acceptable threshold for social science studies, the model only clarifies a modest amount of the variance associated with UR activities. The complexity of human behaviour, especially in areas like estimating participation in recycling, is significantly affected by various hidden influences in social science studies. As a result, it may be impractical to attain elevated levels of precision, recall, or general performance given the current data and model limitations.

Model	Threshold Type	Accuracy	ROC AUC	Recall (Class 1)	Precision (Class 1)	F1-Score	Threshold
Post-SMOTE (Nagelkerke R-squared (Default Threshold): 0.3352)							
Logistic Regression	Default	0.7778	0.6497	0.3832	0.2343	0.2908	0.5000
Logistic Regression	Optimal	0.6578	0.6497	0.5607	0.1869	0.2804	0.4358
LDA	Default	0.7733	0.6547	0.3738	0.2260	0.2817	0.5000
LDA	Optimal	0.6833	0.6547	0.5421	0.1973	0.2893	0.4380
Elastic Net	Default	0.7778	0.6497	0.3832	0.2343	0.2908	0.5000
Elastic Net	Optimal	0.7600	0.6497	0.4206	0.2261	0.2941	0.4812
Random Forest	Default	0.7500	0.5677	0.2617	0.1609	0.1993	0.5000
Random Forest	Optimal	0.8611	0.5677	0.1495	0.3200	0.2038	0.8364
XGBoost	Default	0.7589	0.5739	0.2430	0.1605	0.1933	0.5000
XGBoost	Optimal	0.2767	0.5739	0.9346	0.1344	0.2350	0.0132

Figure S3. Summary of different approaches performed for dealing with data imbalance, focusing on how well the different approaches predicted the actual participants (Recall for ‘yes’).

Logistic Regression Assumptions and Hypothesis Formulation

All assumptions for binomial LRA were assessed and deemed to be reasonably met in this study: The dependent variable DV_2 is dichotomous (called 0 for ‘no’ and 1 for ‘yes’), independent variables IV_i are categorical (nominal or ordinal), observations are assumed to be reasonably independent (justification below), and the categories of the DV_2 and IV_i are mutually exclusive and exhaustive, with each IV_i having more than 15 cases. The H_0 was “none of the independent variables have a significant effect on the probability of the outcome” and the H_A was “at least one independent variable significantly influences the outcome”.

Impact of Non-Random Sampling and Variable Interdependence

Since the sample was not chosen randomly, the dataset analysed in this research may contain potential factors that lead to variables' interdependence (Boyd et al., 2023; Bhattacharjee, 2019). Individuals from the same M_i operate within the same environment and benefit from nearly the same municipal services, a reality that can affect their attitudes. However, the study investigates the disparities that exist between citizens from different localities. Additional factors contributing to a lack of independence could be individuals being part of the same family, which may result in shared beliefs, or attending the same educational institution, where similar concepts are encouraged among all students. Non-independence is a prevalent challenge associated with non-probabilistic samples and in social sciences, which can result in misleading biases and false positive outcomes. Within social sciences, there are two methods for dealing with complex sampling designs: treating the data as if it results from independent random sampling, even though substantial dependencies frequently exist, or making ad hoc adjustments (Fox, 2015). For many inferential statistics, it is essential to assume that the selection of participants is random, but this condition is not fulfilled in the present scenario. However, the outcomes of inferential statistics based on a convenience sample cannot be generalizable, yet they can still present valuable information for targeted contexts, decision-making, or preliminary inquiries. In qualitative research, especially within the fields of education and social sciences, researchers often rely on convenience sampling due to their easy access to specific target groups, especially in order to formulate hypotheses that will be thoroughly examined in future research. According to Hubbard et al. (2019), utilizing non-random sampling paired with a strategy for replication can produce strong and reliable results. The same scholar, agreeing with Freedman (1999), points out that throughout history, scientific progress, both past and ongoing, has been achieved without the implementation of randomization methods.

Table S2. Variance inflation factor (VIF) for assessing multicollinearity among predictors

Variables IV_i		VIF
		const
Mi	M_2 : Grevena	1.244
	M_3 : Kalamaria	1.309
	M_4 : Kavala	1.466
	M_5 : Kordelio-Evosmos	1.161
	M_6 : Larissa	1.265
	M_7 : Neapoli-Sykies	1.208
	M_8 : Pavlos Melas	1.144
	M_9 : Pylaia-Chortiatis	1.443
Sex		1.064
Age		4.448
Education		1.983
Employment status	Secondary/Post-secondary education student	3.099
	Homemaker/Pensioner	1.239
	Unemployed/Other cases	1.099
Marital status	Unmarried (single parents included)	6.818
	Married or in registered partnership (separated included)	5.043
	Widow/er	1.160
Income		1.272
Household size		1.728
Number of children		3.440

Table S3. Participation rates in traditional and used cooking oil recycling within the studied municipalities for weighted sample ($n=3,000$)

Municipality (Mi)	Participation		
	Traditional recycling	UCO recycling	Traditional recyclers that recycle UCO
M1: Ampelokipi-Menemeni	86.2%	10.3%	12.0%
M2: Grevena	90.2%	8.5%	9.4%
M3: Kalamaria	89.7%	19.1%	21.3%
M4: Kavala	60.0%	1.6%	2.6%
M5: Kordelio-Evosmos	78.4%	18.0%	23.0%
M6: Larissa	84.9%	5.4%	6.4%
M7: Neapoli-Sykies	80.3%	14.5%	18.1%
M8: Pavlos Melas	85.0%	19.6%	23.1%
M9: Pylaia-Chortiatis	89.1%	27.3%	30.7%
M10: Thessaloniki	77.5%	11.9%	15.1%
Total	79%	11.9 %	15.1%

Table S4. Strength of association between $IV_{i(1 \rightarrow 12)}^1$ and $DV_{j(1,2)}^2$ based on Cramer's coefficients [V or phi (φ_c or φ)] for weighted and unweighted sample ($n=3,000$)

IV_i^1	DV_j	Unweighted sample		Weighted sample		Change in the strength of association from DV_1 to DV_2
		φ_c or φ	Strength of association ⁴	φ_c or φ	Strength of association ⁴	
IV_1 : M_i^3	DV_1^5	.198***	Strong	.175***	Strong	↓↓↓
	DV_2^6	.188***	Strong	.188***	Strong	-
IV_2 : Sex	DV_1	-.010	Not sig.	-.016	Not sig.	↑
	DV_2	-.056**	Weak	-.057**	Weak	-
IV_3 : Age	DV_1	.157***	Strong	.150***	Strong	↓
	DV_2	.143***	Moderate	.132***	Moderate	↓
IV_4 : Education attainment	DV_1	.143***	Moderate	.122***	Moderate	↓↓
	DV_2	.096***	Weak	.081***	Weak	↓↓
IV_5 : Employment status	DV_1	.111***	Moderate	.107***	Moderate	↓
	DV_2	.079***	Weak	.066**	Weak	↓↓
IV_6 : Marital status	DV_1	.109***	Moderate	.116***	Moderate	↑
	DV_2	.132***	Moderate	.124***	Moderate	↓
IV_7 : Monthly family income	DV_1	.082***	Weak	.080***	Weak	-
	DV_2	.067*	Weak	.060**	Weak	↓
IV_8 : Household size	DV_1	.101***	Moderate	.108***	Moderate	↑
	DV_2	.090***	Weak	.108***	Moderate	↑↑
IV_9 : Number of children	DV_1	.116***	Moderate	.118***	Moderate	-
	DV_2	.149***	Strong	.140***	Moderate	↓
Count of associations	DV_1		8/9		8/9	
	DV_2		9/9		9/9	

Note. ¹ IV_i = independent variable. ² DV_j = dependent variable. ³ M_i = municipality in focus. ⁴Adapted from *User's guide to correlation coefficients* by Akoglu (2018). ⁵ DV_1 = traditional recycling participation. ⁶ DV_2 = used cooking oil participation. p (2-sided): *** $p < .001$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .01$.

Table S5. Feature importance analysis of the post-SMOTE model

IV_i	Feature	Coefficient β	Standardised coefficient β
IV_1	M Kavala	-1.851	-1.851
	M Thessaloniki	-1.380	-1.380
	M Larissa	-1.183	-1.183
	M Grevena	-0.746	-0.746
	Marital status - Unmarried (single parents included)	-0.739	-0.739
	M Neapoli-Sykies	-0.667	-0.667
	M Kalamaria	-0.666	-0.666
	M Pylaia-Chortiatis	-0.632	-0.632
	M Kordelio-Evosmos	-0.523	-0.523
	M Pavlos Melas	-0.483	-0.483
	Sex - Male	-0.478	-0.478
IV_4	Education attainment	-0.367	-0.367
IV_5	Employment status - Secondary/Post-secondary education student	-0.362	-0.362
IV_6	Marital status - Married or in registered partnership (separated included)	-0.308	-0.308
IV_5	Employment status - Unemployed	-0.192	-0.192
IV_6	Marital status - Widow/er	-0.165	-0.165
IV_3	Age	0.164	0.164
IV_5	Employment status - Homemaker/Pensioner	-0.140	-0.140
IV_8	Household size	0.085	0.085
IV_7	Monthly family income	0.032	0.032
IV_9	Number of children	0.024	0.024

Note. IV_i = independent variable.

Note: Each point represents the odds ratio of a category compared to its reference group, with the dashed vertical line indicating the reference value (OR = 1). Results are based on the post-SMOTE logistic regression model.

Figure S4. Forest plot of odds ratios (with 95% confidence intervals) for socio-demographic predictors of household participation in used cooking oil (UCO) recycling.

Baseline (reference case): Thessaloniki, female, 16–25 years old, with up to secondary education, employed/renter, married or in registered partnership, monthly income $\leq 350\text{€}$, living alone with no children.

Scenario 1 (most likely recycler): Pylaia–Chortiatis, female, 36–50 years old, tertiary/post-tertiary education, employed/renter, married or in registered partnership, monthly income $\leq 350\text{€}$, household of 5 members with 2 children.

Scenario 2 (least likely recycler): Kavala, male, 26–35 years old, up to secondary education, student, unmarried, monthly income $>950\text{€}$, living alone with no children.

Scenario 3 (intermediate profile): Kalamaria, female, older than 50, up to secondary education, unemployed/other, widowed, monthly income 751–950€, household of 2 members with 1 child.

Figure S5. Estimated probabilities of participation in UCO recycling by scenario for selected socio-demographic profiles (baseline, most likely, least likely, intermediate).

Table S6. Rates of recycling or household participation in organised used cooking oil collection programmes, as reported in the available literature examining household practices for managing used cooking oil

Study	Recycling/Participation rate ^a
<i>Hanisah et al., 2013</i> Teluk Bahang, Pulau Pinang, Malaysia 30 individuals Households and food business	0-3% (unclear)
<i>Cho et al., 2015</i> South Korea 420 homemakers	10.2%
<i>Haruhiro et al., 2015</i> Bogor city, Indonesia 188 households Distribution of survey via three schools	>6% (unclear)
<i>Hanisah et al., 2015</i> Kampung Nelayan, 380 respondents	(unclear)
<i>Daud et al., 2020</i> PasirGudang, Malaysia	7.6%
<i>De Feo et al., 2020</i> Angri, Salerno, Italy 354 individuals	53.4%
<i>Kamaruzaman et al., 2022</i> Felda Lepar Hilir, Pahang, Malaysia 214 households	8%
<i>Lee et al., 2024</i> 20 cities in Japan 4,160 residents	29.4%
<i>Recoil Project 2012-2015</i> Greece 270 participants	25.8%
<i>Hartini et al., 2019</i> Semarang, Indonesia 347 households	0.9%
<i>Kabir et al., 2014</i> Petaling, Selangor, Malaysia 352 households	12.0%

Note. The articles referenced in the table can be found in the reference section of the paper 'Household used cooking oil recycler: Identifying a profile'. UCO = Used cooking oil. a. The figures pertain to either the recycling percentage, which encompasses self-reuse, or the involvement in a structured UCO programme. In some cases, the data on recycling/participation rate is based on the UCO disposal methods sated from participants.

Table S7. Key factors affecting involvement in participation in used cooking oil recycling programmes: results from the available literature

Study	Factors under examination	Result
Cho et al., 2015 South Korea 420 homemakers 20-65 years old Dependent variable: Participation in UCO recycling programme	Sex	Not significant
	Age	Not significant
	Education	Not significant
	Income	Not significant
	Household size	+ 22.5% (significant at 10%)
Yacob et al., 2015 Petaling, Selangor, Malaysia 352 households Dependent variable: Willingness to participate in UCO recycling programme	Sex (ref: males)	91% females (significant at 10%)
	Age	7% (significant at 1%)
	Education (ref: primary school)	186% university level (significant at 5%)
	Employment	Not significant
	Income	0.1% (significant at 1%)
	Race (ref: Indian)	146% Malay, 269% Chinese (significant at 5%)
De Feo et al., 2020 Angri, Salerno, Italy 354 individuals	Sex	Knowledge of UCO collection system in participant's town (women 15% more informed) Main cause for not to participating in UCO recycling programme (women are too busy, men have bad habits) Survey participant is the only one in the household that recycles UCO (more women)
	Age	Survey participant is the only one in the household that recycles UCO (more common as age grows)
Hidalgo et al., 2020 Guayaquil, Ecuador 441 households Dependent variable: Consumption of cooking oil (ODDS)	Household size	-67% (significant at 5%)
	Number of children	-66% (significant at 5%)
	Number of children 12-18 years old	+940% (significant at 0.1%)
	Number of adults	+267% (significant at 5%)
	Socio-economic status	-0.43% (significant at 10%)
Kamaruzaman et al., 2022 Felda Lepar Hilir, Pahang, Malaysia 214 households	Sex	Awareness on UCO recycling – not associated
Lee et al., 2024 20 cities in Japan 4,160 residents Dependent variable: Participation in UCO recycling programme sample	Sex (ref: females)	+60.2% (significant at 0.1%)
	Age (ref: 60-70s)	20-30s: -25.4% (significant at 5%), 40s: -28.9% (significant at 1%), 50s: -19% (statistically insignificant)
	Education (ref: higher secondary or equivalent)	associate degree or equivalents: -15.2% (not significant), bachelor's or master's degree or equivalents: -19.6% (significant at 5%)
	Household size	Not significant
	Household with one or more children	-17.7% (significant at 10%)

Note. The articles referenced in the table can be found in the reference section of the paper 'Household used cooking oil recycler: Identifying a profile'. UCO = Used cooking oil.

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